

SOME ASPECTS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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***Annotation:** This article comparatively studies the interdependence and differences of Uzbek and English phraseological units, as well as the forms of their translation.*

***Keywords:** synonymy, phraseology, idiom, method, proverb.*

INTRODUCTION

Phraseology has a special place in modern linguistics today. This field has been developing in recent years and a lot of scientific work is being done on it. Phraseology is the knowledge of phrases. Phrases, word associations, are free and stable associations, and in phraseology they are studied in terms of structure and meaning. A phraseological unit is a unit of speech that is a figurative spiritual unit consisting of a combination of more than one independent lexeme: *tepa sochi tikka bo'ldi, boshi osmonga yetdi; to show the right feather, to play the first fiddle*. Phraseological combinations in all languages, especially English phraseological combinations, are also considered to be the folk art of the nation. According to the origin of phraseological compounds in English, scholars divide them into three main groups³⁸:

1. Old phraseological compounds in English
2. Phraseological compounds learned from other languages
3. Phraseological compounds derived from the American version of English

³⁸ Ginsburg R.S. A Course in Modern English Lexicology. M., 2019

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phraseological units are directly related to the ancient customs, historical realities and traditions of the English people. Many of the phraseological associations reflect the traditions and beliefs of the English people, the historical truths of English history that we know and do not know. Many English idioms are derived from works of art, various literature, and are the source of their origins, such as the works of writers, children's poetry, fairy tales, and cartoons. For example, the English writer William Shakespeare contributed greatly to the enrichment of the English dictionary. The phraseology he created is second only to the Bible. Here are some of them³⁹:

Cakes and ale - (s.s.) *pirojnoye va pivo; tashvishsiz quvonch, hayotdan zavqlanmoq.*

A fool's paradise - *hayoldagi baxt, hayolot dunyosi.*

Give the devil his due - *dushmanga tan bermoq.*

He green-eyed monster - *yashil ko`zli berahm odam; rashkchi.*

Have an itching palm - *poraxo`rlik qilmoq; tamagir.*

Lay it on with a trowel – *bo`rttirib maqtamoq, haddan tashqari maqtamoq*

Not to care a fig – *hammaga birdek bo`lmoq*

That's got him – *qilmish-qidirmish*

There is a deer – *ziyrak bo`ling!*

I am fed up with it! – *jonga tegdi! Yetadi!*

A.Mamatov, one of the linguists studying the field of phraseology, studies Uzbek phraseological compounds in terms of their formation and divides them into 4 classifications:

1. Phraseologisms formed in relation to a person's activities and psyche: *ko`ngli ochiq, hafsalasi pir bo`lmoq, yerga ura ko`kka sapchimoq* etc.

2. Phraseologisms formed in connection with the profession: *bo`zchining mokisidek.*

³⁹ Mednikova E.M .. Seminars in English Lexicology. M., 2018. 30.

3. Phraseologisms based on animal images: *oyog'i kuygan tovuqday, ammamning buzog'iday, to'ygan qo'zi*, etc.

4. Phraseologisms formed in terms of religious affiliation: *xudo ko'tarsin*.

Phraseologisms, as well as lexemes, have synonyms, antonyms, and homonyms. According to H. Jalmonkhanov, on the basis of such an relationship phraseological synonymy and phraseological antonymy are formed.

For example, *og'zi qulog'ida* and *boshi osmonga yetdi* are synonymous with each other, both of which express joy and happiness. Ascending to heaven and doing one with the earth are mutually antonymous units.

To get the bit between one's teeth *o'zini tuta olmaslik*

To take the bit between one's teeth *o'zidan ketmoq*

To nip in the bud *ildizini quritmoq*

To check in the bud *ildizini quritmoq*

To leave no stone unturned *barcha imkoniyatlarni ishga solmoq*

To move heaven and earth *qo'lidan kelganini qilmoq*

These phrases are synonymous.

In English, too, phraseological units are brought to the speech in a ready-made form, which cannot be replaced by other words, and this helps to make the speech more figurative. Idioms are compounds that are understandable to everyone in speech and are easy to use in direct speech. In English, as in Uzbek, there are many synonyms, antonyms and homonyms. For example, a dark house - mysterious and black ceiling - these two compounds, which are distinguished from others by their mysterious meanings, can be synonymous with each other.

English idioms, like the above, are phraseological units belonging to the group of animals, such as black ship, dark house. Phraseological units make speech more beautiful and enrich language. Many English, Russian and Uzbek scholars have conducted research on their origin, history and formation. The English linguist L. Graff described the phraseological compounds and the differences in their methodological

connections. And he says that the word *breakfast* also comes from the compound to *break fast*⁴⁰.

CONCLUSION

In short, every language is colorful and rich in phraseology. Applying them in our daily lives will make our speech more beautiful and fluent. From the analysis of the phraseological combinations discussed above, it can be said that Phraseology should be studied as an independent science, not as a branch of linguistics.

Particular attention should be paid to the correct use of phraseological units in speech, translating them from one language to another. These units determine how much vocabulary a language has, in addition to giving emotional or expressiveness and imagery to a speech or literary text.

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